

USING COOPERATIVE METHODS IN FORMING THE SOCIAL ACTIVITIES OF STUDENTS

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Abstract. This article talks about the application of cooperation technology in practical processes and its importance, based on paying attention to the factors and criteria that are considered important in the formation of social activity in the student. At the same time, the reader will learn from this article about the meanings of the concept of "social activity" that are interpreted today, views on its importance; The student analyzes how the formation of social activity of young people is becoming a necessity today and its reasons.

Keywords: Social activity, student, organization, mobility, student personality.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola talaba shaxsida ijtimoiy faollikni shakllantirishda muhim sanaladigan omillar va mezonlarga e'tibor berish asosida hamkorlik texnologiyasini amaliy jarayonlarda qo'llash, uning ahamiyati haqida so'z yuritadi. Shuning barobarida o'quvchi bu maqoladan «ijtimoiy faoliyat» tushunchasining bugungi kunda talqin qilinayotgan ma'nolari to'g'risida, uning ahamiyati borasidagi qarashlarni; talaba yoshlarning ijtimoiy faolligini shakllantirish bugun nechog'lik zaruratga aylanayotgani hamda uning sabablarini tahlil qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Ijtimoiy faoliyat, talaba, tashkilotchilik, harakatchanlik, talaba shaxsi.

Аннотация. В данной статье говорится о применении технологии сотрудничества в практических процессах и ее значении, основанном на обращении внимания на факторы и критерии, которые считаются важными в формировании социальной активности студента. Вместе с тем из данной

статьи читатель узнает о значениях понятия «социальная активность», которые трактуются сегодня, взглядах на ее значение; Студент анализирует, как формирование социальной активности молодежи сегодня становится необходимостью и ее причины.

Ключевые слова: Социальная активность, студент, организация, мобильность, личность студента.

In our republic, special attention is paid to the improvement of the content of higher education and the processes of personnel training based on advanced foreign experiences, to the development of social competencies in students as an important direction of spiritual and educational work. At the same time, there is a need to improve the pedagogical mechanisms of achieving a full understanding of the social significance of students' professional activities, finding a suitable solution to the responsibility for social demands and obligations. In the "Strategy of Actions" aimed at the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "In the process of educating young people who are physically healthy, spiritually and intellectually developed, independent-thinking, loyal to the Motherland, with a firm outlook on life, deepening democratic reforms and developing civil society significant and important tasks such as "increasing their social activity" were set. This requires clarifying the pedagogical and psychological characteristics of the development of social activity of students, the pedagogical model of the development of social activity, and the use of interactive and modern technologies in the formation of the content of classes outside the auditorium.¹

Therefore, first of all, it is necessary to study what and how social activity is and the factors and criteria of forming social activity of students, and then apply technologies. Today, the concept of "social activity" is interpreted in a broad and

¹ "Xalq ta'limi" ilmiy –metodik jurnali 2022 №6 Hilola Abjalova "Ijtimoiy hamkorlik asosida talabalarning pedagogik tayyorgarligini takomillashtirish"

narrow sense. In a broad and narrow sense, social activity is understood as a quality that reflects the level of sociality of a person, that is, his connections with the social whole, readiness to act in the interests of society, the depth of acceptance of public interests, and in a narrow sense, social activity means, is understood as a quality that expresses the connection of a person with a certain social community. We will consider the category of "social activity" in this scientific article in a narrow sense. Today, the modern educational space needs professionally competent, socially active and competitive personnel, specialists who are ready to provide a stable, safe and successful society. Because society is putting more complex tasks before humanity. In such processes, the society needs professionals to determine their own destiny, to be self-aware, to think freely and independently, in other words, to be socially active individuals. Based on this, it can be said that society needs modern knowledge. Independent, ethical, proactive people can make responsible decisions in the chosen situation, predicting their possible consequences; methods of cooperation, mobility, dynamism, constructiveness, a sense of responsibility for the fate of the country are developed, in a word, socially active persons will be in the center of the field in this place.²

In this regard, today the sociality of the individual is increasing and gaining importance. The student person plays an important role in the life of the society because the student is a social group that manifests itself in activities of high social significance, consciously aimed at solving the problems facing the society. We can also call them future potential opportunities. Student youth are a unique social group. It follows that it contains all the characteristics of youth, and also confirms it with the following characteristics: *activities related to education at the university; * the most educated youth group; *reserve for replenishment of knowledge workers; * an integral part of the intelligentsia; *heterogeneity of social

² Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti ilmiy axborotlar ilmiy nazariy jurnali 2023 1-son Abjalova Hilola "Ijtimoiy hamkorlik asosida talabalarning pedagogik tayyorgarligini takomillashtirish"

origin; *self-awareness of a certain group; *community of interest and subculture. It is necessary to form the social activity of students. In this, of course, on the one hand, it is permissible to act taking into account the changing social characteristics, and on the other hand, the specific characteristics of this socio-demographic group, its internal stratification, its place and role in society, as well as among young people it is necessary to solve the existing conflicting aspect of needs and not to forget about it as a social subject and the possibilities of their implementation. A number of factors are considered important in forming the social activity of students. These factors are: the desire of young people for self-realization, an effective state policy for young people, as well as interesting and influential people for young people. At the same time, we also face factors that hinder the formation of social activity among students. For example, distrust, indifference to the problems of older age groups, weak trust in authorities, indifference to students themselves are among them.³

It is also important to manage the formation of social activity in students. In this case, the main criterion of the effectiveness of managing the social formation of students is the high level of student activity in all types of activities and the high level of compatibility of interests with the interests of other social entities. Therefore, based on these recognitions, it is possible to witness the importance of paying close attention to the necessary factors in the formation of social activity in students. Based on these factors, the use of collaborative technology in the process will be effective. Because the idea of cooperative education is not only to do the tasks together, but also to read, search and learn in cooperation. To increase the social activity of students, teaching on the basis of this technology is to teach every student to fundamental intensive mental work, to think creatively and independently, to educate consciousness and independence as a person, to create a

³ “Xalq ta’limi”ilmiy –metodik jurnali 2022 №6 Hilola Abjalova “Ijtimoiy hamkorlik asosida talabalarning pedagogik tayyorgarligini takomillashtirish”

sense of personal dignity in every student. , implies strengthening of confidence, as a result of paying attention to educational processes and forming a sense of responsibility in learning. In short, educating the growing young generation in the spirit of social activity is one of the urgent tasks of today. As defined in the basic law of independent Uzbekistan, the society's perspective, development and development path is to establish a legal, democratic, humane civil society. Building such a society largely depends on the formation of students' skills of organization, initiative, flexibility, and, in general, social activity.

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- 3 Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti ilmiy axborotlar ilmiy nazariy jurnali 2023 1-son Abjalova Hilola “Ijtimoiy hamkorlik asosida talabalarning pedagogik tayyorgarligini takomillashtirish”